

MONETARY POLICY AND COMMERCIAL BANKS PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIAN BANKING SECTOR

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Abstract: *The study investigates the impact of monetary policy on the performance of the Nigerian banking sector from 1980 to 2023. To achieve the study objective of evaluating the impact of monetary policy instruments on the performance of the Nigeria commercial banks time series data were collected from the publications of Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), International Monetary Fund (IMF); and subjected to post estimation for unit root. Monetary policy instruments have been a veritable tool for economic management. Vector Auto regression (VAR) and Autoregressive Distributed Lag techniques (ARDL) were adopted as the method of analysis. Our findings show that various monetary policy instruments notably monetary policy rate, money supply growth and treasury bill rate were instrumental in driving the profit and Loans performance of commercial banks in Nigeria in the study period. Specifically, a shock to commercial banks profit by monetary policy rate, money supply growth and Treasury bill rate produced positive impact on commercial banks profit that are statistically significant at various levels of significance throughout the period after a time lag. Our findings also shows that monetary policy instruments were however slower in Domestic savings mobilization drive in the banking system. To deepen commercial banks performance in Nigeria further, we recommend policies that will make income to the people inclusive to boost domestic savings and a lagged-effect consideration in the administration of monetary policy in Nigeria.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The banking is an important sector in the economy as the financial needs of all the other sectors are met through the banking system. The banking sector provides the liquidity lubricant needed for goods and services to be

effectively distributed across all sectors of the economy. The performance of the macro economy is dependent on the performance of the banking sector. The banking sector has to be efficiently positioned to cater for the liquidity and credit needs of the economy, failing which,

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leads to financial and general slowdown of growth in the economy. As experiences shows, mal-functioning of the financial system, of which the banking system is at its core, results in declining output growth, notably the 2007-2008 global economic meltdown that was as a result of financial crisis of the world economic leaders (Eke, Eke & Inyang (2015).

To enable the banking system functions efficiently, a systemic regulation has to be in place. This is the role of monetary policy. Monetary policy works through the banking system adjusting financial prices and propagating the desired volume of funds for economic activities. The instruments of monetary policy do not affect economic activities directly rather they work through their effects on the commercial banks and capital market (Ajayi &Atanda, 2012; Asobari & Christian,2023) . Thus, monetary policy may have their first impact on the deposit taking institutions through their influence on the availability of liquid resources of the system. More than that, the dominance of the commercial banks in outplay of financial performance of most emerging economies is not disputed, and Nigeria is a witness to this fact in her economy (Bassey & Ekong, 2019).

Monetary policy is one of the important keys of macroeconomic management, the other being the fiscal policy key. When in use, monetary policy is a two side of the same coin. When the economy experiences declining growth, expansionary monetary policy is expected to

move the economy back to positive production growth path. However, when the economy's growth path is explosive such that inflation-induced growth is seen, a contractionary monetary policy helps to bring down economic activities and stabilized prices (Ekong & Ukoha, 2018). Leahy (1993) found out that be it expansionary or contractionary policy, monetary policy have a substantial influence on the rate and pattern of economic growth by influencing the volume and disposition of saving as well as the volume and productivity of investment.

The phase of monetary development of a region may affect the conduct of monetary policy of that region for efficient banking performance. For most economies, monetary development is continually being reformed to suit the general growth characteristics of the economy. For instance in Nigeria, the economic policy thrust of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) has divided our financial sector into phases. Thus, financial development literature categorizes monetary policy in Nigeria as passing through regimes such as pre and post SAP and pre and post consolidation of the 2004 (Bassey & Ekong, 2019). More than this, the phase of development of the financial sector itself from controlled to uncontrolled financial regimes has affected the development of monetary policy, changing the policy instruments from direct to indirect. The general argument is that by their changes, these phases have either intrinsically or explicitly reshaped the behaviour of

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monetary policies and hence their outcomes in the general economy (Ajayi & Atanda, 2012).

Commercial banks performance indicates the readiness of the banking system to meet its constitutional role of dispensing financial resources in appropriate measures to the rest of the economy. Commercial bank performance is also seen as the accomplishment of a given bank function measured against preset known Banking Standard of service delivery. It is deemed to be the fulfillment of financial rules and obligation of delivering value returns on shareholders wealth on the one hand and servicing the financial needs of the entire economy on the other, in a manner that releases the bank(s) from all liabilities. According to Ekpenyong, Abdullahi and Ademola (2025), bank profitability, savings mobilization, credit creation and liquidity management are crucial indications of commercial bank performance. In most cases, bank performance is measured against Uniform Bank Performance report by say a body for such investigation, notably the Central bank of Nigeria (CBN) or the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC).

The above introduction provides the basis for this study, which is an attempt to investigate the strength of monetary policy as a catalyst to economic performance, but this time, with special attention on the performance of the commercial banking system as the core of the financial system in Nigeria. Ekong and Ukoha, (2018) highlighted at least three reasons that such exercise is plausible. First, the world

financial meltdown of the recent past continues to produce spill-over effect on susceptible economies, thus requiring continuous examination of our policies in mitigating such trend. In-fact, as could be gleaned from the crisis, the management of monetary portfolio is not a smooth business. Second, now that the Nigerian economy is out of recession, policy fine tuning for improved sectoral performance is imperative for it to stay in positive growth trajectories. Third, global changes through technology, trade and investment continues to expose each community in the global space to new economic challenges. Thus, a policy stance that was once plausible may not be effective any more.

A review of empirical literature revealed a staggering deterioration in the performance indexes for Nigerian commercial banks over time. For instance, Return on Equity fluctuates downward between 23.3, 14.7 and 12.2. from 1989 to 1990. It further dipped from 45.9 in 1993 to 12.62 in 1994 and settled at 5.27 in 1995. Between 2001 and 2006, the return on equity declined from 114.3% to 4.12% and further declined to -0.46% in 2016. However, Return on Equity was up from 15.5 % to 23.5 % between 2020 to 2022. Also, the non-performing loans of the banking system rose up to 47.4 % in 1989 and 45.5% in 1999, and, even when it had reduced, only settles at 14.2% in 2010 and 2.96 % in 2014, higher than the 3% globally accepted for a sound banking system. It further increases

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to 4.01 % in 2022, below the CBN regulatory threshold of 5%.

The downward performance of commercial banks performance indexes was in sharp contrast with the conduct of money supply as an anchor of monetary policy in Nigeria. For example the growth rate of money supply was 5.9 percent in 1981, but grew to 14.02 percent in 1983. It further grew from about 9 percent in 1985 to almost 33 percent in 1988; has maintained a steady growth from 13 percent in 1989 to a peak of almost 64 percent in 1993 and even when it should decline, has continue to maintain a high double digit of almost 20 percent in 1995. From 1996 to the year 2000, money supply growth jumped from 16 percent to almost 49 percent. Such upward swing was also observed for the years 2003 to 2007 where it grew steadily from 13.5 percent to 65 percent before declining, but maintaining double digits for most of the years up to 11.6 percent in 2016. It further increased in 2019 to 14.2 %. Money supply continued it upward trajectory reaching a high of 20.2 % in 2020. According to Nigeria Central Bank, money supply growth follows the nominal needs of servicing economic activities (CBN, 2018; Ekong & Mboho, 2021). This high growth of money supply to the economy rightfully reflects the policy direction of monetary policy makers. The commercial banks draw from this high growth rate and make interest yielding advances to grow their profit.

Within the period also, the price-based anchor of monetary policy (monetary policy rate)

showed declining trend for most of the years. For instance, the year 1993 to 1997 witnessed a significant decline in MPR from 26 percent to 13.5 percent in 1994 and remained stable up until 1997. Similar falling trends were also seen for 2002-2007 periods where a consistent yearly decline of not less than 2 percent from 19 percent to 8 percent appeared. Also, monetary policy rate from 2012 to 2015 fell from 12 % to 11 %. It was further reduced from 13.5 % in 2019 to 11.5 % in 2021. Such downward trends have the tendency of triggering increased financial flows in the banking system that may have tinkered on their revenue base and profitability, savings mobilization and lending behaviour of banks that the study seeks to investigate.

The current mismatched in the trend of monetary policy conduct and commercial banks performance indices necessitated the interest of this study which examines the impact of monetary policy on the performance behaviour of commercial banks in terms of profitability, savings mobilization and lending behaviour.

The main objective of the study is to empirically investigate the impact of monetary policy on commercial bank profitability performance in Nigeria from 1980 to 2023. The specific objectives are to examine the impact of monetary policy instruments(monetary policy rate, money supply, cash reserve ratio and treasury bill rate) on commercial bank profitability, lending and domestic savings.

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2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Bank Performance

Commercial Bank Performance refers to their ability to generate sustainable profits, manage risks, and support economic growth through efficient financial intermediation. Performance is typically assessed through profitability indicators such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and net interest margin, as well as non-financial factors including operational efficiency, risk management, and customer satisfaction (Banna et al., 2021). Commercial bank performance is the accomplishment of a given bank function measured against preset known Banking Standard of service delivery. Bank performance is deemed to be the fulfillment of financial rules and obligation of delivering value returns on shareholders wealth on the one hand and servicing the financial needs of the entire economy on the other, in a manner that releases the bank(s) from all liabilities. Furthermore, bank profitability, savings mobilization, credit creation and liquidity management are crucial indicator of banks performance. (Ekpenyong et al., 2025). Over the years, economic literature pays a great deal of attention to the performance of banks, expressed in terms of competition, concentration, efficiency, productivity and profitability. Profitability is a bank's first line of defense against unexpected

losses, as it strengthens its capital position and improves future profitability through the investment of retained earnings.

2.1.2 Concept of Monetary Policy

The concept of monetary policy has been variously defined, it can be view as a credit control measures adopted by the central Bank of a country. Azeez and Ilori (2021), see monetary policy as the management of interest rates and money in circulation which is generally carried out by the Central Banks. Furthermore, Lyndon and Godspowe (2019) defined monetary policy as one in which systemic actions are carried out by CBN through the highest bank of a nation to regulate the cost and availability of funds within the system thus helping to attain specified goals that the government wants to carry out. The definition implies among other things that the aims of monetary policy are essentially to regulate the quantity, availability and cost of money n the economy in order to control inflation and spur sustainable economic growth.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Monetarist Theory

An important anchored of this study is an economic school of thought called monetarist, this school of thought is led by Professor Milton Friedman. The monetarist basically adopted the quantity theory of money to illustrate their theory, as a theory of demand for money and not a theory of output price. Monetarist believed on the indirect pass-through of monetary policy to the economy (the interest rate mechanism) and more strongly, on a direct process of

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citizens portfolio adjustment. The argument is that the public portfolio balance consists of a wide variety of assets such as bonds, equities, bills, shares, commercial papers savings, mortgages, etc. Thus, when the central bank purchases securities in open market, it sets in motion a portfolio disturbance through the substitution and wealth effects on citizens' portfolios. If the portfolio imbalance increases income in the hands of the citizens, they could spend it on buying liquid assets and near money, which increases their market price. These effects will ultimately increase aggregate money demand and expand output. Onakoya, Ogundajo and Johnson (2017) argued that this course has similar implications for other sub-sectors of the national economy.

2.2.2 Efficient Structure Hypothesis

Efficient Structural Theory (ESH) is another postulation for studying the performance of commercial bank. According to Grygorenko (2009) theoretical attempt to explain the "weakness" of SCH was provided by Demsetz (1973). He stated that higher profits of banks are not due to their collusive behavior but because of high efficiency level, which, in turn, leads to larger market shares that banks possess. In other words, performance of commercial bank is determined not by the market concentration but by bank efficiency. Market share of the bank is assumed to be a measure of efficiency here. Thus, efficient banks in the market lead to increase in the firms' size and market share due to their aggressive

behavior. This behavior of the efficient banks allowed such firms to concentrate and earn higher profits with further enhancing their market share. Such firms can maximize profits either by maintaining the present level of product price or service charge and firms' size or by reducing their service charge and expanding the firm size (Smirlock, 1985).

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

Onoh (2017) investigated the effect of monetary policy on the performance of commercial banks in Nigeria from 1980 to 2015. In his analysis, his proxy's turnover ratio, Bank Assets and Loan and Advances as commercial banks performance index, while cash reserve ratios, liquidity ratio, monetary policy rate and money supply ratio were used as the policy variables. Utilizing multiple regression technique for data analysis, he found that monetary policy had some level of effect on bank performance the study period. However, the effect was instrument sensitive, i.e, some monetary policy tools work better on some bank performance indexes while such may not work on some other ones.

Borio, Gambacorta and Hofmann (2015) examines the influence of monetary policy on the profitability of commercial banks in 14 advanced economies of Belgium, Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, Sweden, Switzerland, the United Kingdom, and the United States, Austria, Australia and Spain. The samples are annualized data from 109 banks which cover 18 years from 1995 to 2012, a

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period spanning different economic cycles. Their panel analysis results showed a positive relationship between the level of short-term rates (a monetary policy measure) and the slope of commercial banks profitability curve (interest rate structure) and directly on bank profitability. However, their result also showed that beyond a certain point on the profitability curve, policy effects can erode bank profitability implying that policy tradeoff threshold should be seriously sought for.

Afolabi, Adeyemi, Salawuddeen and Fagbemi (2018) examine the importance Monetary Policy and Bank Credit in Nigeria from 1981-2016. The study employed Toda and Yamamoto granger non-causality model. The findings revealed that structural changes in monetary policy system exerted positive significant impact on loan and advances of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. .

Also, Ekong and Mboho (2021) studied the relationship between monetary policy and domestic savings mobilization in Nigeria for the period 1980 to 2019. The study employed Autoregressive Distributed Lag technique on the variables used. The results showed that monetary policy conduct was ineffective in enhancing domestic savings in commercial banks. The study further revealed that, the economy level of income showed evidence of accelerated domestic savings. Hence, to deepen domestic savings mobilization in Nigeria, they recommended income policies that drive domestic savings in the economy such as equitable redistribution among other things.

Ogbulu, Uruakpa and Umezina (2015) when they investigated the nature of the relationship between deposit rates (disaggregated into various categories of deposit rates charged by DMBs) and deposit mobilization in Nigeria within the periods 1981 and 2012. Utilizing a combination of multiple regression and vector error correction mechanism, they found no significant relationship between all categories of deposit rates and total deposit liabilities of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria in the period. Near similar results were also obtained with respect to the impact of deposit rates on time savings and foreign currency deposits. They therefore concluded that a policy of interest rate liberalization alone may not be enough to induce higher levels of fund mobilization.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts ex-post facto research design in the investigation. Ex-post facto research design involves the ascertaining of the effect of past factors on the present happening or event. This research design is adopted for this study because of its strengths and when it is impossible to manipulate the variables since an Ex-post facto design presumes that the data are collected after the events of interest have occurred.

3.2 Model Specification

The study in an attempt to explain the impact of monetary policy on commercial performance, specified three models following Okumoko & Akarara (2016), Ekong & Ukoha (2018) and

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Ojeaga,Ojeagu & Odejimi (2013) but with some modification as;

$$nim = \int (mpr, Ms, Crr, Tbr) \dots \dots \dots 1$$

$$LoA = \int (mpr, Ms, r, Crr, Dep,) \dots \dots \dots 2$$

$$Dep = \int (mpr, Ms, Tbr, NPL, Dr) \dots \dots \dots 3$$

Parameters used for Bank performance our dependent variables are;
 NIM= Net interest margin (commercial bank profitability index)
 LOA= Loan and Advances
 DEP= Deposits mobilized by commercial banks
 Our independent variables-monetary policy was represented by;
 MPR= Monetary policy rate
 MS = Money supply
 CRR= Cash reserve ratio

TBR= Treasury bill rate

4. ANALYSIS OF DATA

4.1 Unit Root Test

The unit root test of the variables for the study is presented in Table 4.1. As Table 4.1 shows, the variables for the study exhibited various levels of stationarity not exceeding second level of stationarity thus making them amendable for our analysis. We used Augmented Dickey Fuller test and the PP test.

Table 4.1: Unit root test results

variables	P P test			ADF test		
	Level	1 st diff	p-value	Level	1 st diff	p-value
<i>Mpr_t</i>	-2.9021*	-7.8329***	0.0000	-2.3162**		0.0264
<i>M2_t</i>	-4.5009***		0.0334	-4.4347***		0.0045
<i>LoA_t</i>	4.3847	-3.0878**	0.0365	-0.8591	-1.9391*	0.0758
<i>tbr_t</i>	-2.6775*	-7.1896***	0.0000	-2.2860**		0.0282
<i>Npl_t</i>	-5.9409***		0.0000	-6.6246***		0.0000
<i>CRR_t</i>	-4.1850***		0.0004	-1.6131	-3.9094***	0.0052
<i>R_t</i>	-2.3611*	-8.4979***	0.0000	-2.5340*	-6.8670***	0.0000
<i>Nim_t</i>	-2.3294	-9.1244***	0.0000	-2.4129	-9.1244***	0.0000
<i>Dep_t</i>	-1.6146	-9.2232***	0.0000	-1.7441	-6.0045	0.0000
<i>Dr_t</i>	-2.8015*	-7.9758***	0.0000	-2.99228*	-3.3629**	0.0196

Note: *, **, *** indicates significance at 10, 5 and 1 percent

Δ indicates the difference operator

Source: Researchers

4.2 The Vector Autoregression Analysis (VAR)

We used the vector autoregression technique to analysed the impact of monetary policy on the profitability of commercial banks in the study

period. The result of the VAR estimates is presented in Table 4.2. Table 4.2 shows that monetary policy rate had positive effect of about 0.27 units on bank performance, money supply growth had positive effect of about 0.04 units

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on bank performance, treasury bill rate had positive effect of about 0.36 units on bank performance, all statistically significance and cash reserve ratio had an insignificant positive

effect of about 0.07 units on bank performance at first instance. As time passes, the effect weakens.

Table 4.2: Vector Autoregression Estimate

Dependent Variable: NIM

	NIM	MPR	MS	CRR	TBR
NIM(-1)	0.427939 (0.19947) [2.14537]	0.272961 (0.07426) [3.67564]	0.044743 (0.08764) [0.51054]	0.070804 (0.08925) [0.79335]	0.364304 (0.12250) [2.97380]
NIM(-2)	0.397241 (0.21519) [1.84604]	-0.244858 (0.08011) [-3.05642]	-0.032236 (0.09454) [-0.34096]	-0.038691 (0.09628) [-0.40187]	-0.484996 (0.13216) [-3.66989]
MPR(-1)	-0.672495 (0.62977) [-1.06784]	-0.629668 (0.23446) [-2.68561]	0.255119 (0.27670) [0.92202]	-0.615966 (0.28177) [-2.18606]	-0.441383 (0.38677) [-1.14120]
MPR(-2)	-0.014770 (0.62359) [-0.02369]	-0.118706 (0.23216) [-0.51131]	0.322694 (0.27398) [1.17780]	-0.022016 (0.27900) [-0.07891]	0.594713 (0.38297) [1.55288]
MS(-1)	-0.016048 (0.30767) [-0.05216]	-0.297819 (0.11454) [-2.60005]	1.069584 (0.13518) [7.91244]	-0.208336 (0.13766) [-1.51345]	-0.174395 (0.18895) [-0.92295]
MS(-2)	-0.188953 (0.29256) [-0.64587]	-0.025053 (0.10892) [-0.23002]	-0.161750 (0.12854) [-1.25839]	0.404810 (0.13089) [3.09265]	0.131691 (0.17967) [0.73295]
CRR(-1)	-0.411243 (0.39811) [-1.03300]	0.116622 (0.14821) [0.78685]	0.154351 (0.17491) [0.88245]	0.859336 (0.17812) [4.82449]	0.378129 (0.24450) [1.54657]
CRR(-2)	0.455049 (0.44649) [1.01918]	0.036574 (0.16622) [0.22003]	-0.142551 (0.19617) [-0.72668]	0.019802 (0.19977) [0.09912]	-0.391195 (0.27421) [-1.42664]
TBR(-1)	0.218590 (0.41304) [0.52922]	0.941151 (0.15377) [6.12035]	0.029425 (0.18147) [0.16214]	0.558280 (0.18480) [3.02095]	1.051122 (0.25367) [4.14368]

TBR(-2)	0.346327 (0.61555) [0.56263]	0.165237 (0.22917) [0.72103]	-0.559843 (0.27045) [-2.07004]	0.134673 (0.27541) [0.48899]	-0.411563 (0.37804) [-1.08868]
C	6.447216 (6.56070) [0.98270]	11.33145 (2.44252) [4.63924]	1.403084 (2.88251) [0.48676]	-2.682422 (2.93537) [-0.91383]	4.946737 (4.02923) [1.22771]
R-squared	0.666124	0.867945	0.906083	0.930611	0.530116
Adj. R-squared	0.453657	0.783910	0.846318	0.886455	0.231098
Sum sq. resids	507.6405	70.36106	97.99378	101.6205	248.7530
S.E. equation	4.803600	1.788360	2.110512	2.149213	3.362582
F-statistic	3.135193	10.32837	15.16069	21.07529	1.772859
Log likelihood	-100.9496	-64.39108	-70.51947	-71.19179	-87.75327
Akaike AIC	6.267544	4.291410	4.622674	4.659016	5.554231
Schwarz SC	6.920618	4.944485	5.275749	5.312091	6.207305
Mean dependent	11.10649	13.17135	15.85351	8.297297	4.232973
S.D. dependent	6.498815	3.847135	5.383643	6.378152	3.834753
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)		7165388.			
Determinant resid covariance		188272.3			
Log likelihood		-592.1995			
Akaike information criterion		37.68646			
Schwarz criterion		42.25798			
Number of coefficients		105			

Source: Researchers

4.3 Autoregressive Distributed Lag Analysis (ARDL) for Loans Performance

When the performance of the banking system in terms of the financial assistance to the productive sector of the economy is concern was examined, we found interesting insight into the relationship. We perform the bound test analysis to ascertain whether there is any

verifiable relationship that should be investigated and reported the result in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: F-Bound Test Results

Null Hypothesis: No levels Relationship

Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	15.10990	10%	1.99	2.94
K	6	5%	2.27	3.28
		2.5%	2.55	3.61
		1%	2.88	3.99

Source: Researchers

Our calculated F value of 15.11 is greater than the theoretical F value of 2.27 lower bound and 3.28 upper bound values at 5 percent level of significance allow us to reject the null hypothesis of no relationship. That means there is a valid variables relationship that should be investigated. Next, we examined the lag

structure of the relationship. This will ensure that all information in the variables are intact due to appropriate lag specification. After examining over 2000 different lag structure for the study, the lag specification of ARDL (1,2,2,1,2,2,0) was selected for the study and reported on Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Lag Selected ARDL (1,2,2,1,2,2,0)

Selection Criteria: Akaike Information Criteria

Source: Researchers

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Thus, we present the results of the short run relationship in Table 4.4.

As Table 4.4 shows, a rise in monetary policy rate will produce statistically significant falling effect on commercial banks loan assistance to the economy of not less than 84 percent at first

impact.. Our model is a good fit as about 83 percent of variations in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables in the system. Our DW value of 2.8 frees our estimates of autocorrelation bias. Thus, our short run results are reliable.

Table 4.4: Short Run Results of Loan performance to Monetary Policy Impact
Dependent Variable: Credit to the private sector

Variable	Coefficien	t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MPR	-8.4480		2.3493	-3.5959	0.0021
MPR(-1)	4.4835		2.3807	1.8833	0.0759
MS	7.9987		1.0019	7.9838	0.0000
MS(-1)	7.5952		2.1242	3.5755	0.0022
CRR	-10.5316		2.9966	-3.5145	0.0025
Dep	8.5938		3.9311	2.1861	0.0423
Dep(-1)	-18.8836		9.2849	-2.0338	0.0570
ECM	-0.1756		0.0136	-12.9118	0.0000
R-squared	0.888555	Mean dependent var	608.4692		
Adjusted R-squared	0.839519	S.D. dependent var	976.9254		
S.E. of regression	391.3568	Akaike info criterion	15.03372		
Sum squared resid	3829003.	Schwarz criterion	15.55618		
Log likelihood	-266.1239	Hannan-Quinn criter.	15.21791		
Durbin-Watson stat	2.806909				

Source: Researchers

In the long run, further increase in monetary policy rate will be detrimental to the general economy as over 9.0 basis points of loans from

the banking system to the private sector may be lost by the sector

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Table 4.5: Long Run Result of Commercial Banks Performance (Loan)Dependent Variable: Credit Assistance to the Private Sector

Variable	Coefficien			
	t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Mpr	-9.9535	2.6289	-3.7862	0.0014
MS	11.4608	5.2375	4.9922	0.0001
CRR	-12.8472	3.6525	-2.1882	0.0001
Dep	2.5487	5.9014	0.4319	0.6710
C	3.4016	2.0381	1.6690	0.1124

Source: Researchers

4.3 Autoregressive Distributed Lag Analysis (ARDL) for Savings Performance

We also investigate the impact monetary policy on the savings mobilization of the commercial banking system. The bound test analysis of the relation is reported on Table 4.6. Table 4.6

Table 4.6: F-Bound Test for Monetary Policy-Savings Mobilization
Null Hypothesis: No levels Relationship

Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	6.691833	10%	1.99	2.94
K	6	5%	2.27	3.28
		2.5%	2.55	3.61
		1%	2.88	3.99

Source: Researcher

Source: Researcher

shows that the derived F-value of 6.7 greater than the critical bounds values of 2.27 and 3.28 percents respectively suggest a possible long run relationship that should be investigated. Thus, we accept the hypothesis of a relationship between the variables of interest.

We proceed to examine the lag structure of the relationship. As reported in Figure 4.2, after a systematic evaluation of more than 2000

related relations, the lag structure of ARDL(2,2,0,2,1,2,0) was adjudged stable and hence selected for the study.

Figure 4.2: Lag Selected ARDL (2,2,0,1,2,0)

Selection Criteria: Akaike Information Criteria

Source: Researchers

The short run analysis of monetary policy effect on commercial banks domestic savings mobilization is presented in Table 4.7. As shown on Table 4.7, monetary policy rate produces statistically significant negative effect on domestic savings mobilization by almost 24 percentage point. However, this may not last as still within the period, citizens may experience incentives to save their funds through positive rise in mpr. Also, a rise in treasury bill rate will dipped domestic saving drive by at least 69percent in the short run and may even dipped

further as time passes. A rise in tbr may trigger more return on investment incentives on the citizens who may readjust their portfolio in favour of treasury bills than savings. Within the period also, domestic savings may improve due to the improved position of commercial banks balance sheet as a result of positive non-performing loans position. Our explanatory variables explain over 56 percent of variations in the dependent variable showing a good fit of our model. The DW value of 2.4 shows that our variables were not authocorrelated.

Table 4.7: Short Run Results of Monetary Policy and Savings Mobilization
Dependent Variable: Private Domestic Savings (Dep)

Variable	Coefficien	t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Dep(-1)	-0.245277	0.125325	-1.957123	0.0638	
Mpr	2.118086	0.516365	4.101917	0.0005	
mpr(-1)	1.820780	0.475855	3.826336	0.0010	
Tbr	-0.697143	0.390848	-1.783667	0.0889	
tbr(-1)	-1.310626	0.448231	-2.923997	0.0081	
Npl	0.035400	0.126875	0.279015	0.7830	
Npl(-1)	-0.175009	0.063478	-2.757013	0.0118	
ECM	-0.231296	0.043165	-5.358440	0.0000	
R-squared	0.658893	Mean dependent var	-1.907297		
Adjusted R-squared	0.561434	S.D. dependent var	8.171198		
S.E. of regression	5.411322	Akaike info criterion	6.422637		
Sum squared resid	819.9075	Schwarz criterion	6.814482		
Log likelihood	-109.8188	Hannan-Quinn criter.	6.560781		
Durbin-Watson stat	2.355448				

Source: Researchers

The long run results of monetary policy and commercial banks savings mobilization performance is presented in Table 4.8. As the result shows, a rise in monetary policy rate will grow domestic savings in the economy by more than 5percent and statistically significant. Over time, citizens may perceive the rise in mpr to be a boost in returns on investment and hence raise their deposit. However, a percentage rise in money supply will dipped domestic savings by 0.11 percent in the long run but not significant. Such negative effect is also exhibited

by treasury bill rate. A percentage rise in tbr will significantly dipped domestic savings by more than 3 percent in the long run. A rise in tbr may trigger more return on investment incentives on the citizens who may readjust their portfolio in favour of treasury bills than savings that started from the short run. As mpr rises, other rates in the economy rise and so do deposit rates

Table 4.8: Long Run results of Monetary Policy and Savings Mobilization
Dependent Variable: Domestic Savings

Variable	Coefficien			
	t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Mpr	0.052830	0.025143	2.101200	0.0455
MS	-0.001133	0.012357	-0.091679	0.9277
	-			
Tbr	0.034988	0.019389	-1.804472	0.0828
NPL	0.001972	0.001630	1.210143	0.2371
Dr	0.005607	0.012491	0.448872	0.6572
C	0.094161	0.047054	2.001138	0.0559

Source: Researchers

4.3 Discussion of Findings

Our analysis of the impact of monetary policy on commercial banks performance has shown that monetary policy positively impacted on key banking performance indices. For instance key policy tools, notably monetary policy rate, money supply growth and changes in treasury bill rates were shown to generate rising revenue impacts on commercial banks profitability. This means that commercial banks capitalizes on the risings volumes of funds to engaged on healthy competitions and ultimately raised their profit margin for good return on investment to their shareholders. This findings is consistent with the findings of Borio, Gambacorta & Hofmann (2015) who examined the influence of monetary policy on the profitability of commercial banks

in 14 advanced economies of Europe and found similar positive influences.

While monetary policy generally impacted positively on bank performance during the period, the study reveals that most of the loans advanced by commercial banks to the economy were from commercial banks savings mobilization drive. Domestic savings generated positive significant impact on loan assistance to the economy up to 85 percentage point on a single change. The implication here is that a healthy banking system in itself can generate adequate savings that could cater for the investment needs of the economy.

However, while the effects of monetary policy on commercial banks performance were stronger for profit drive and loans assistance to private investors, their effects were much slower

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for domestic savings mobilization. Many key policy variables had negative effects on domestic savings or no impact at all (like the case of money supply in the short run). This finding is consistent with the finding of Ekong and Mboho (2021), which reported that key variables of monetary policy were weak in driving domestic savings in Nigeria. Ogbulu et al.(2017) also found similar outcome when they investigated the relationship that exist between deposit rates and deposit mobilization in Nigeria within the periods 1981 to 2012 and found no significant relationship between all categories of deposit rates and total deposit liabilities of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, we investigated the impact of monetary policy on the performance of the Nigerian banking system from 1980 to 2023. Findings suggests that various monetary policy variables notably monetary policy rate, money supply growth and treasury bill rate were instrumental in driving the profit and Loans performance of commercial banks in Nigeria in the study period. Specifically, a shock to commercial banks profit by monetary policy rate, money supply growth and Treasury bill rate produced positive impact on commercial banks profit that are statistically significant at various levels of significance throughout the period. Also when the effect of monetary policy on commercial banks loan performance to the private economy was examined, we made the

following observations, that within the short run, a rise in monetary policy rate will produce statistically significant falling effect on commercial banks loan assistance to the economy of not less than 84 percent at first impact. But, as time passes, the negative effect fades away. In the long run, further increase in monetary policy rate will be detrimental to the general economy as over 9.0 basic points of loans from the banking system to the private sector may be lost by the sector. Furthermore, a rise in Money supply produces statistically significant positive loan effect from the banking system to the general economy throughout the short run period and into the long run. The study also observed that changes in the cash reserve ratio will produce significant negative impact on commercial banks loan assistance to the economy throughout the study period. However, monetary policy variables were much slower in driving Domestic savings in the banking system. Monetary policy rate produces statistically significant negative effect on domestic savings mobilization of almost 24 percentage decline while a rise in treasury bill rate will dipped domestic saving drive by at least 69 percent in the short run and may even dipped further as time passes. To deepen commercial banks performance in Nigeria further, we suggest policies that will make income to the people inclusive to boost domestic savings.

Based on empirical evidence that changes in monetary policy will produce larger impact on

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banking performance, for instance, monetary policy rate producing about 24 percentage effect on domestic savings mobilization treasury bill rate producing at least 69 percent, we recommend moderation in the application of policy as larger impact will be felt by the public.

Also, monetary policy instruments had outstanding positive impact from the VAR analysis. Therefore, we recommend that such instruments as monetary policy rate, money supply growth and treasury bill rate should be used in moderation to continue to help the banking system to grow in delivering value addition to the general economy.

Our finding also shows that the effect of policies on the dependent variables changes even within the short run, for instance the case of monetary policy rate impact on loan performance of commercial banks where over 80 percent decline was seen to about 9 percent positive after one lag suggests that monetary policy effect on banking performance will be a time-lagged thing. We suggest the lagged-effect consideration in the administration of monetary policy in Nigeria.

Our study also shows that most of the loans assistance by commercial banks to the economy was generated by domestic private savings. We recommend income policies that drive domestic savings in the economy such as equitable distribution of income that made financial inclusion pro-poor.

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